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Cyclodextrin-modified nanodiamond for the sensitive fluorometric determination of doxorubicin in urine based on its differential affinity towards β / γ -cyclodextrins

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Abstract

The manuscript reports on the preparation of β -cyclodextrin-modified nanodiamonds (β CD-ND) for the extraction and preconcentration of the fluorescent anticancer drug doxorubicin (DOX) from biological samples. The inclusion of DOX into the cavities of β - and γ -cyclodextrin (CD) confirms their utility for selective extraction and elution of the drug based on its good fit to the cyclodextrin cavity. Although both larger cyclodextrins (β CD and γ CD) accommodate DOX, DOX clearly prefers the bigger γ CD cavities. Dispersive micro solid-phase extraction using β CD-ND as sorbent enables the inclusion complexation of DOX. The elution of DOX from β CD-ND cavities occurs with a basic solution of γ CD containing 10% acetonitrile owing to the preferential affinity (i.e. optimal fit) of DOX into the larger γ CD cavity. DOX is quantified by monitoring its intrinsic fluorescence (exc/em = 475/595 nm). The method can determine DOX in urine with a limit of detection of 18 ng·mL⁻¹. Recoveries (93.2% and 94.0%) and precision (RSDs of 5.9% and 4.7%) at 100 and 400 ng·mL⁻¹ DOX levels in urine are

satisfactory. The matrix effect is negligible even when working with undiluted urine samples. Graphical abstract Nanodiamonds functionalized with β -cyclodextrin (β CD-ND) were used as sorbent for the determination of nanomolar levels of doxorubicin (DOX). It is based on host:guest interactions ruled by different stabilities of DOX within cyclodextrin (CD) cavity-size: β CD/ γ CD.

Keywords: Cyclodextrin affinity; Extraction; Fluorescence; Inclusion complexes; Surface functionalization.

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